

Short Notes on Our Ancestors who Could not Leave Legacy

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I have been working about physical laws for a long time. During this period, I think found some information out about secrets of ancient civilizations. The thing which ignited the curiosity on me was a star which is called Tariq in Koran as the star of piercing darkness. Also there are some information about Nibiru that is believed in the gods in the heaven made it visible. These are interesting; because I was noticed that there can be another size black hole can be visible afterwards. Also I noticed that there are some heavenly information about aliens. I decided to make an investigation about them; but there are so many things, worked about 1-2 weeks and I bored; so I decided to publish my findings as short notes about our ancestors who could not leave legacy. It is not an advanced research. Just overhearing about some possibilities, if there is any body different than us?

1 Traces of the Ancient Ones in God Word

[LOG 0]

We will show them our proofs on the horizons, and in their very souls, until it becomes clear to them that it is the truth. Is it not sufficient that your Lord is witness over everything? [Koran 41: 53]

[LOG X] This verse is the summary of the God's all wishes from the world people whatever their religions are for this world in accordance with the compassionate title of him. Just keep it and remember me when the day came up. He had chosen some enemies for you to show yourself to God.

1.1 Traces of the ancient ones

[LOG 1]

Have they not traveled in the land and seen what was the end of those who were before them? They were superior to them in strength and in the traces in the land. But Allah seized them with chastisement for their sins. And none had they to protect them from Allah. [Koran 40:21]

[LOG 1a] Interesting words. Could be? Really had more advanced civilizations been lived some times ago? What happened then, and why? I am in a wonderment state; but who are 'they' and 'those' in this verse? The comparison is for whom? I require more information.

[LOG 2]

Have they not journeyed through the land, and seen the outcome for those before them? They were more numerous than they, and had greater power and influence in the land. But what they had achieved availed them nothing. When their messengers came to them with clear proofs, they rejoiced in the knowledge they had, and the very things they used to ridicule besieged them. [Koran 40:82,83]

Have they not traveled the earth and seen how those before them ended up? They were more powerful than them, and they cultivated the land and developed it more than they developed it, and their messengers came to them with clear signs. God would never wrong them, but they used to wrong themselves. [Koran 30:9]

[LOG 2a] There are some early ancient civilizations which had lived before ancient civilizations. There is no 'you' addressing, by intending the people who had lived during or after 7th Century. There is a comparison between early ancient

civilizations and the ancient civilizations which had lived after them.

[LOG 2b] Waywardness is not running out of sight again as usual. Oh those ancients... Somehow they could not make a living. How hard could it be?

[LOG 3]

They denied the truth when it has come to them; but soon will reach them the news of what they used to ridicule. Have they not considered how many generations We destroyed before them? We had established them on earth more firmly than We established you, and We sent the clouds pouring down abundant rain on them, and We made rivers flow beneath them. But We destroyed them for their sins, and established other civilizations after them. [Koran 6:5,6]

[LOG 3a] Here is some additional information as comparison material. Here, directly 'you' had been used by intending the people who had lived during or after 7th Century.

[LOG 3b] Also 'soon will reach them' may be second evidence.

[LOG 3c] The sentence 'established other civilizations after them' is not running out of sight. How could it be? Was this renewing in the earth or from space? Was there any other human civilization in space somewhere. Even maybe another type creature? Is there any trace even as a tale, as a rumor, as written information?

[LOG 4]

Glory be to Him who created all the pairs; of what the earth produces, and of their own selves, and of what they do not know. [Koran 36:36]

[LOG 4a] I think I found something useful. There is a word as 'pairs'. Why is not just 'pair'? It is plural, and also is of 'what they human does not know'. Are there any other living things which are different than animals, vegetation and human. If it is true, these mysterious creatures also have gender; thus must multiply.

[LOG 5: Journey of a ruler]

He pursued a certain course. Until, when he reached the setting of the sun, he found it setting in a murky spring, and found a people in its vicinity. [Koran 18:85,86]

Then he pursued a course. Until, when he reached the rising of the sun, he found it rising on a people for whom We had provided no shelter from it. [Koran 18:89,90]

Until, when he reached the point separating the two barriers, he found beside them a people who could barely understand what is said. They said, "O Zulqarnayn, the Gog and Magog are spreading chaos in the land. Can we pay you, to build between us and them a wall?" [Koran 18:93,94]

[LOG 5a] Seems I found primal legendary ones while I was searching the traces of the ancient ones. A nation who have no shelter against the Sun? This clearly means they have no atmosphere? These seem aliens.

[LOG 6]

And of his signs are the creation of the heavens and the earth, and the creatures He has spread throughout them; and He is Able to gather them at will. [Koran 42:29]

[LOG 6a] This can be counted as an evidence. Here, creatures had been spread throughout the heavens and the earth. Why cannot exist some other creatures in space somewhere? Even they can be human.

[LOG 7]

Then, when nations before you disregarded what they were reminded of, we opened for them the gates of all things. Until, when they delighted in what they were given, we seized them suddenly; and at once, they were in despair. [Koran 6:44]

[LOG 7a] Here is some information, that seems, God gave many information to them to improve their abilities. It means also they were advanced in any subject.

[LOG 8]

I looked, and I saw a windstorm coming out of the north—an immense cloud with flashing lightning and surrounded by brilliant light. The center of the fire looked like glowing metal, and in the fire was what looked like four living creatures. In appearance their form was human, but each of them had four faces and four wings. Their legs were straight; their feet were like those of a calf and gleamed like burnished bronze. Under their wings on their four sides they had human hands. All four of them had faces and wings, and the wings of one touched the wings of another. Each one went straight ahead; they did not turn as they moved. [Ezekiel 1: 4-10]

1.2 Possible formation of existent creatures

[LOG 9]

We created the human being from clay, from molded mud. And the jinn We created before, from piercing fire. Your Lord said to the angels, "I am creating a human being from clay, from molded mud." "When I have formed him, and breathed into him of My spirit, fall down prostrating before him." So the angels prostrated themselves, all together. Except for Satan. He refused to be among those who prostrated themselves. He said, "O Satan, what kept you from being among those who prostrated themselves?" He said, "I am not about to prostrate myself before a human being, whom You created from clay, from molded mud." He said, "Then get out of here, for you are an outcast". [Koran 15: 26-34]

Although He created you in stages. And God germinated you from the earth like plants. Then He will return you into it, and will bring you out again. [Koran 71: 14,16,17]

We created man from an extract of clay. Then We made him a seed, in a secure repository. Then We developed the seed into a clot. Then We developed the clot into a lump. Then We developed the lump into bones. Then We clothed the bones with flesh. Then We produced it into another creature. Most Blessed is God, the Best of Creators. Then, after that, you will die. Then, on the Day of Resurrection, you will be resurrected. [Koran 23: 12-16]

God created you from dust, then from a small drop; then He made you pairs. No female conceives, or delivers, except with His knowledge. No living thing advances in years, or its life is shortened, except it be in a Record. That is surely easy for God. [Koran 35: 11]

He who perfected everything He created, and originated the creation of man from clay. Then made his proliferation from an extract of an weak fluid. Then He proportioned him, and breathed into him of His Spirit. Then He gave you the hearing, and the eyesight, and the brains—but rarely do you give thanks.[Koran 32: 7,8,9]

O people! If you are in doubt about the Resurrection—We created you from dust, then from a small drop, then from a clinging clot, then from a lump of flesh, partly developed and partly undeveloped. In order to clarify things for you. And We settle in the wombs whatever We will for a designated term, and then We bring you out as infants, until you reach your full strength. And some of you will pass away, and some of you will be returned to the vilest age, so that he may not know, after having known. And you see the earth still; but when We send down water on it, it vibrates, and swells, and grows all kinds of lovely pairs. [Koran 22: 5]

The likeness of Jesus in God's sight is that of Adam; He created him from dust, then said to him, "Be," and he was. [Koran 3: 59]

And of His signs is that He created you from dust; and behold, you become humans spreading out. [Koran 3: 59]

And Abraham, when he said to his people, "Worship God, and fear Him. That is better for you, if you only knew. Have they not seen how God originates the creation, and then reproduces it? This is easy for God." [Koran 29: 16,19]

What is the matter with you, that you do not appreciate God's Greatness? Although He created you in stages. Do you not realize that God created seven heavens in layers? And He set the moon in their midst for light, and He made the sun a lamp. And God germinated you from the earth like plants. Then He will return you into it, and will bring you out again. [Koran 71: 13,18]

[LOG 9a] It is clearly visible, that somehow human had been created from mud. These verses are counted as evidence for evolution.

[LOG 9b] Also the question of -have they not seen how God originates the creation- may be counted as an evidence for an advanced civilization. It seems, they knew the secrets of evolution.

[LOG 10: Fallen spirituals or psychics]

And it came to pass when man commenced to multiply upon the face of the earth, and daughters were born to them. That the sons of the nobles saw the daughters of man when they were beautifying themselves, and they took for themselves wives from whomever they chose. And the Lord said, "Let My spirit not quarrel forever concerning man, because he is also flesh, and his days shall be a hundred and twenty years." The Nephilim were on the earth in those days, and also afterward, when the sons of the nobles would come to the daughters of man, and they would bear for them; they are the mighty men, who were of old, the men of renown. [Genesis 6: 1-4]

[LOG 11]

It happened after the sons of men had multiplied in those days, that daughters were born to them, elegant and beautiful. And when the angels, the sons of heaven, beheld them, they became enamoured of them, saying to each other, Come, let us select for ourselves wives from the progeny of men, and let us beget children. Then their leader Samyaza said to them; I fear that you may perhaps be indisposed to the performance of this enterprise; And that I alone shall suffer for so grievous a crime. But they answered him and said; We all swear; And bind ourselves by mutual execrations, that we will not change our intention, but execute our projected undertaking. Then they swore all together, and all bound themselves by mutual execrations. Their whole number was two hundred, who descended upon Ardis, which is the top of mount Armon. That mountain therefore was called Armon, because they had sworn upon it, and bound themselves by mutual execrations. These are the names of their chiefs: Samyaza, who was their leader, Urakabameel, Akibeel, Tamiel, Ramuel, Danel, Azkeel, Saraknyal, Asael, Armers, Batraal, Anane, Zavebe, Samsaveel, Ertael, Turel, Yomyael, Arazyal. These were the prefects of the two hundred angels, and the remainder were all with them. Then they took wives, each choosing for himself; whom they began to approach, and with whom they cohabited; teaching them sorcery, incantations, and the dividing of roots and trees. And the women conceiving brought forth giants, Whose stature was each three hundred cubits. These devoured all which the labor of men produced; until it became impossible to feed them; When they turned themselves against men, in order to devour them; And began to injure birds, beasts, reptiles, and fishes, to eat their flesh one after another, and to drink their blood. Then the earth reproved the unrighteous. [The book of Enoch: Chapter 7, Fall of Angels]

[LOG 12: Rape of geni.]

On the Day when He gathers them all together: "O assembly of jinn, you have ex-

ploited multitudes of humans." Their adherents among mankind will say, "Our Lord, we have profited from one another, but we have reached the term that you have assigned for us." He will say, "The Fire is your dwelling, wherein you will remain, except as God wills. Your Lord is Wise and Informed. Thus We make some of the wrongdoers befriend one another, because of what they used to do. "O assembly of jinn and humans, did there not come to you messengers from among you, relating to you My revelations, and warning you of the meeting of this Day of yours?" They will say, "We testify against ourselves." The life of the world seduced them. They will testify against themselves that they were disbelievers. [Koran 6: 128-130]

[LOG 13]

On the Day when He gathers them all together, then say to the angels, "Was it you these used to worship?" They will say, "Be You glorified; You are our Master, not them. In fact, they used to worship the jinn, and most of them had faith in them." [Koran 34: 40,41]

[LOG 13a] Remember the beginning of [LOG 9]. God called angles. God did not say such as angles and geni. He only called angles. After that he said that only genie rejected. Namely, genie rejected between angles. It clearly means that angle means the creature who is not material. They can be spatial fire as also can be luminous.

[LOG 13b] According to these information, sometimes the word of divine can be used for angles; but it does not mean holy such as Gabriel. It actually means spatial, spiritual or ghostly.

[LOG 14: Angel worship.]

You will be bombarded with flares of fire and brass, and you will not succeed. [Koran 55: 35]

[LOG 14a] This also can be counted as an evidence to the formation of geni. Here, the fire is flaming. It is not spatial wave. It is classic world fire.

[LOG 15]

Solomon said, "O notables, which one of you will bring me her throne before they come to me in submission?" An imp of the sprites said, "I will bring it to you before you rise from your seat. I am strong and reliable enough to do it." [Koran 27: 38, 39]

[LOG 15a] Also as we know, name of these spiritual existence called as power holders. The same is also used for power holders of the nature muscle strength. These powers are not living things; but sometimes it is understood in this manner as wrongly. This is an expression which can be used for anything. This verse can be counted as an evidence for this.

1.3 Specific creatures

[LOG 16]

And when the Word has fallen on them, We will bring out for them from the earth a creature which will say to them that the people are uncertain of Our revelations. [Koran 27: 82]

[LOG 16a] Here, God may speak in the name of the creature, that actually means God shall not like your behavior and shall punish you by a creature. Namely the creature here does not have to speak such in this verse. You must understand that you are wrong with your claim about God.

[LOG 17]

In that day the Lord, with his great and strong and cruel sword, will send punishment on Leviathan, the quick-moving snake, and on Leviathan, the twisted snake; and he will put to death the dragon which is in the sea. [Isaiah 27: 1]

[LOG 18]

O Lord, how great is the number of your works in wisdom you have made them all; the earth is full of the things you have made. There is the great, wide sea, where there are living things, great and small, more than may be numbered. There go the ships; there is that great beast, which you have made as a play-thing. [Psalms 104: 24-26]

[LOG 19]

For from the past God is my King, working salvation in the earth. The sea was parted in two by your strength; the heads of the great sea-beasts were broken. The heads of the great snake were crushed by you; you gave them as food to the fishes of the sea. [Psalms 74: 12-14]

[LOG 20]

See now the Great Beast, whom I made, even as I made you; he takes grass for food, like the ox. His strength is in his body, and his force in the muscles of his stomach. His tail is curving like a cedar; the muscles of his legs are joined together. His bones are pipes of brass, his legs are like rods of iron. He is the chief of the ways of God, made by him for his pleasure. He takes the produce of the mountains, where all the beasts of the field are at play. He takes his rest under the trees of the river, and in the pool, under the shade of the water-plants. He is covered by the branches of the trees; the grasses of the stream are round him. Truly, if the river is overflowing, it gives him no cause for fear; he has no sense of danger, even if Jordan is rushing against his mouth. Will anyone take him when he is on the watch, or put metal teeth through his nose? [Job 40: 15-24]

[LOG 21]

Is it possible for Leviathan to be pulled out with a fish-hook, or for a hook to be put through the bone of his mouth? Will you put a cord into his nose, or take him away with a cord round his tongue? Will he make prayers to you, or say soft words to you? Will he make an agreement with you, so that you may take him as a servant for ever? Will you make sport with him, as with a bird? or put him in chains for your young women? Will the fishermen make profit out of him? will they have him cut up for the traders? Will you put sharp-pointed irons into his skin, or fish-spears into his head? Only put your hand on him, and see what a fight you will have; you will not do it again! Truly, the hope of his attacker is false; he is overcome even on seeing him! He is so cruel that no one is ready to go against him. Who then is able to keep his place before me? Who ever went against me, and got the better of me? There is no one under heaven! I will not keep quiet about the parts of his body, or about his power, and the strength of his frame. Who has

ever taken off his outer skin? who may come inside his inner coat of iron? Who has made open the doors of his face? Fear is round about his teeth. His back is made of lines of plates, joined tight together, one against the other, like a stamp. One is so near to the other that no air may come between them. They take a grip of one another; they are joined together, so that they may not be parted. His sneezings give out flames, and his eyes are like the eyes of the dawn. Out of his mouth go burning lights, and flames of fire are jumping up. Smoke comes out of his nose, like a pot boiling on the fire. His breath puts fire to coals, and a flame goes out of his mouth. Strength is in his neck, and fear goes dancing before him. The plates of his flesh are joined together, fixed, and not to be moved. His heart is as strong as a stone, hard as the lower crushing-stone. When he gets ready for the fight, the strong are overcome with fear. The sword may come near him but is not able to go through him; the spear, or the arrow, or the sharp-pointed iron. Iron is to him as dry grass, and brass as soft wood. The arrow is not able to put him to flight: stones are no more to him than dry stems. A thick stick is no better than a leaf of grass, and he makes sport of the onrush of the spear. Under him are sharp edges of broken pots: as if he was pulling a grain-crushing instrument over the wet earth. The deep is boiling like a pot of spices, and the sea like a perfume-vessel. After him his way is shining, so that the deep seems white. On earth there is not another like him, who is made without fear. Everything which is high goes in fear of him; he is king over all the sons of pride. [Job 41: 1-34]

[LOG 21a] The most detailed information about the creature.

[LOG 22]

That day has been prepared for the elect as a day of covenant; and for sinners as a day of inquisition. In that day shall be distributed for food two monsters; a female monster, whose name is Leviathan, dwelling in the depths of the sea, above the springs of waters; And a male monster, whose name is Behemoth; which possesses, moving on his breast, the invisible wilderness. His name was Den-dayen in the east of the garden, where the elect and the righteous will dwell; where he received it from my ancestor, who was man, from Adam the first of men, whom the Lord of spirits made. Then I asked of another angel to show me the power of those monsters, how they became separated, how they became separated on the same day, one being in the depths of the sea, and one in the dry desert. And he said, You, son of man, are here desirous of understanding secret things. And the angel of peace, who was with me, said, These two monsters are by the power of God prepared to become food, that the punishment of God may not be in vain. Then shall children be slain with their mothers, and sons with their fathers. And when the punishment of the Lord of spirits shall continue, upon them shall it continue, that the punishment of the Lord of spirits may not take place in vain. After that, judgment

shall exist with mercy and longsuffering. [The book of Enoch 58: 6-14]

[LOG 22a] The above stated verses seem evidence for the creature of [LOG 16] as also they support each other.

2 Strange Locals of Interstellar Medium

2.1 People of Mount Qaf side

[LOG 23: Words of Muhammad]

Jabliesa and Jablieca are two metropolitan cities. One of them is at east and the other one is at west. Eastern one is called as Jablieca. It was made of green emerald, and both of them are approached to the Mount Qaf. Each city has 2000 parasang in both width and length. His cousin Ali asked, "Are these cities from this earth which we exist?" He answered, "These are in darkness, are approached to the Mount Qaf." Ali asked, "How many people are there in each city?" He answered, "Castle of each city has 1000 pieces bastion. 1000 persons guard each bastion every night. These 1000 persons does not take turn again until 1 year completed. Ali asked, "Why do they guard this castle?" He answered, "They guard; because there are many nations at that side. There is a hostility between the other nations and these people of Jabliesa and Jablieca. They always make war, night and morning. They keep watch because of this." Ali asked, "Are these people of Jabliesa and Jablieca humankind?" He answered, "They do not know is there human in this world." Ali asked, "Does not Satan worm their way?" He answered, "Also they do not know does Satan exist." Ali asked, "Do not those stars, the Moon, the Sun rise on them?" He answered, "Also they do not know did God create the Moon, the Sun and stars." Ali asked, "How could they sight?" He answered, "Their brightness is from gleam of the Mount Qaf. Their stones and walls shine like radiance." Ali asked, "What do they eat and drink?" He answered, "They do not drink or eat anything." Ali asked, "What do they wear?" He answered, "Their body do not require dress." Ali asked, "Are they angles?" He answered, "They are not angles; but they are similar to angles in obedience." Ali asked, "Do they make child?" He answered, "All of them are male. There is no female between them." Ali asked, "What is their religion? Are they destined for heaven or hell?" He answered, "They are people of heaven. They are about Islam. Gabriel transferred me to that side during the night I ascended. I notified Islam to them. They became Muslims. They believed in God and me. I taught one of them the rules of Islam, and left him as khalif. After that, Gabriel transferred me to side of Pharis, Phidie, Gog and Magog, Moensel, Bhakiel and Noories. Also I notified Islam to them. They declined. All of them are unbeliever." Ali asked, "Can any person arrive them from our people?" He answered, "No! Nobody is able to arrive them; because traveled four months in darkness; but three persons from people of Aad had believed in prophet Hud, and they escaped persecution of the people of Aad, and settled that metropolitan city." After that some people from Jewry

had been placed around him said, that " You are right. Also we found these 3 persons in Torah such. These escaping people settled that realm of Jabliesa and Jablieca. They could not exit from there since they feared from people of Phidie. [From the commentary of Tabari]

[LOG 23a] Two legendary metropolitan cities. Their destinations are confusing. What is the reference? The Sun? Maybe east is Neptune side, and west is Mercury side even if the distance is exceeded towards Mercury or Neptune. What is Mount Qaf? Where is it? Is this only an expression of a heavenly body like asteroid belt?

[LOG 23b] Size of the cities is extremely huge. 1 parasang is 12.000 human step, is also a distance which a person takes in 1 hour, is also 3 nautical miles or nearly 5.5 kilometers. It means, each one of them has nearly 121.000.000 km^2 surface area, that is almost big like the earth ground. A city like this is charming especially if it was made of green emerald.

[LOG 23c] There are some other nations. Seems they are also in a battle. It means somehow they manufacture battle equipment. Also it does not run out of sight, that some of these nations are unreliable since frightened of them, whatever the reason is, for protecting the motherland or annoyance without reason.

[LOG 24d] The escaping people who are from the people of Aad, had high technology equipment or was just a miracle from God? How could we know this? Was Aad an advanced civilization? I cannot get more information from this text. This is a different research topic; but here is a short information about Aad.

[LOG 25]

We had given Aad the force and the fortune which we did not give to you; and we gave them the hearing, and the sight, and the minds; but neither their hearing, nor their sight, nor their minds availed them in any way. That is because they disregarded the revelations of God; and so they became surrounded by what they used to ridicule. [Koran 46:26]

[LOG 25a] If the hearing and the sight make a sign to high technology, and if the minds sign to scientific, intellectual information, then we can say they were advanced civilization. I do not know the truth; but if is by some machines, also somehow had the heavenly ones come here before partially?

[LOG 25b] Over this record [LOG 23], some new type creatures have strange properties must be recorded. Some of them are only male and they are not nourished; even so they do not die; but what about the others?

[LOG 26: Words of Muhammad]

Gog and Magog are generations of Adam. If they are sent to humans, they consume life of humans. They shall not die until each one of them leaves over 1000 children from their own posterity. They consist of three classes; Dhaveal, Tarnaise and Mensek. [Rudani, C.5, H.no: 9930, s.372]

[LOG 26a] Here is also some additional information about Gog and Magog. As it can be seen, they are not immortal or long lasting. They die after they made enough children.

2.2 Long lasting ones

[LOG 26b] Over this record [LOG 23], it can be said, that they are eastern people. Over [LOG 23], it can also be said, that they are exactly from sky. They are exactly extraterrestrial life form; because the answer of the question "Are these

cities from this earth which we exist?" is "These are in darkness, are approached to the Mount Qaf." Already it can be detected over [LOG 5], that there is no shelter means atmosphere against star.

[LOG 27]

He said, "My Lord, relieve me until the day they are resurrected." He said, "You are of those given respite. Until the day of the time appointed." [Koran 15:36,37,38]

He said, "Give me respite, until the Day they are resurrected." He said, "You are of those given respite." [Koran 7:14,15]

[LOG 27a] Here, what is the meaning of "those given respite"? It seems, that there had already been some other creatures who live until the resurrection. They are not immortal; but extremely long lasting community. Maybe they are known as immortal even if they are not.

[LOG 27b] Remember [LOG 4]. There were something which are of "what they human does not know". Seems that there are some other type creatures which human has not experienced contact yet.

[LOG 27c] These information are enough, and render possible to exist of different kind creatures, that are different than genii and angles.

2.3 Realm of Terror

[LOG 28: Words of Muhammad]

Gog is a community alone, and also Magog is a community alone. Each community has 400.000 people, and anyone of these do not die until they see 1000 armed men from own children. They consist of three classes. One of their class is like Aeres. Aeres is a tree in Damascus, that it is 120 ells in length. It rises towards sky. Here are these, neither mountain nor iron endures. The other class from them sleep such, that they lay one of their ears low to ground, and make the other ear quilt. Elephant, wild animal, camel, pig, whatever they see, they eat. If one of between them dies, also they eat that dead. One day, one tip of their multitudinous group shall take place in Damascus, and the other tip shall be in Khorassan. [İbn Mâce 4079]

Genii and humans are consist of ten parts.

Gog and Magog includes nine parts of them, and humankind includes one part of them.

[Could not find again the reference]

[LOG 28a] Remember [LOG 5]. There were some people who were waiting for help against anarchic Gog and Magog. They were also eastern people like Gog and Magog.

[LOG 28b] Remember [LOG 23], that they are in a battle. There is an information at [LOG 5], that they have no shelter against the Sun. It seems they are the people of Jabliesa. Also these are the people who are waiting help against the anarchic.

[LOG 28c] It seems, that they shall visit the earth one day. I do not think so; but I hope they only say "Hello world!".

[LOG 29]

The barrier of Gog and Magog shall be opened. They conquer the earth like God said "they attack from each hill". Muslims retreat because of them by leaving their places. Remaining Muslims there take refuge in own cities and castles, and shelter own cattle and sheep on their side. Gog and Magog visit a river, and drink by consuming its water. Last part of them also visit that lake. One of between them says, that "Once, here was wa-

ter". They dominate the earth. One of between them says, that "We have finished the community of the earth. Now we shall make battle with community of the heaven." One of them throws his spear towards sky, and the spear turns back as bloody manner. Upon this, Gog and Magog says, that "We also killed the community of the heaven." Upon this, God sends animals like herd of camel worm. These animals catch them from their necks, and they die like death of grasshopper herd by falling onto each other. At the morning, Muslims do not hear their voices. Upon this, Muslims say, that "Who is going to search what they do now, at the expense of own life." Upon this, a man who made himself ready against them comes up, and finds Gog and Magog as died. Upon this, he calls Muslims by saying, "Attention! I herald, that our enemies had died." Upon this, Muslims come out, and unleash their animals; but the animals cannot find grass to eat but flesh of Gog and Magog. How animals get fat in the best manner when they get fat, in the same manner, they get fat by eating flesh of them. [İbn Mâce, Fiten 33]

[LOG 29a] Here is another information about their visit.

[LOG 29b] It seems, that they cannot tolerate God phenomenon. They are extremely arrogant. They more like love anarchy. If it is not an expression, it seems, that they have no high technological equipment. Seems they shall dominate by their population; but the opposite is pretty possible.

[LOG 29c] He says they shall dominate all the world; but why there are only Muslims and their lands in the texts? Are their starting points on their lands?

[LOG 30]

Until, when Gog and Magog are let loose, and they swarm down from every mound. The promise of truth has drawn near. The eyes of those who disbelieved will stare in horror, "Woe to us. We were oblivious to this. In fact, we were wrongdoers." [Koran 21:96,97]

[LOG 30a] Here is another information about their visit. Sounds not so good.

[LOG 30b] The usual performance of supposed realist and rational persons does not run out of sight again. I wish they never existed. They always leave a bad legacy. They consume us in information, and make us lost time almost about every subject. What self confidence? Their all lessons had always completed, and they do not make any mistake. Like skepticism is weakness for them.

[LOG 31: Words of Muhammad]

As Gog and Magog reached the day light since they dig the barrier everyday, their chief says, that "Leave the excavation work, and turn back. We will continue tomorrow." Upon this, God repairs the barrier like before. At the end when their deadline is over and God wants to send them towards humans, again they dig and as they reached the day light, their chief says again, that "Leave the excavation work, and turn back. We will continue tomorrow by the grace of God." They answer back, "by the grace of God." The following day they arrive to the barrier again. This time they find it as they left it. Upon this, they continue the digging, and then come out to humans. They drink and consume each water when they occurred. [İbn

Mâce, Fiten (Turmoil) 27]

[LOG 35a] Here is another information about their visit. This time there are some additional information about them like their place and behavior.

[LOG 32: Words of Muhammad]

The demons kept begging Jesus not to send them into the bottomless pit. [Luke 8:31]

[LOG 32a] Here a destination information about their place.

3 Extraterrestrial Migration of Ancient People: Interstellar earthling

[LOG 33: Words of Muhammad]

During my ascension, I saw a city full of people beyond Mount Qaf. When they saw me as well, they said, "O Muhammad! Thank to God who has been showed your face to us." and they believed in me. I taught them rules of sharia, and asked "Who are you?". They told me those: "O Muhammad! We are from children of Israel. When Moses died, a disagreement appeared between the children of Israel. Seditious spread between us. Such that, once they killed 43 prophets at once. When their prophets were murdered, some of us who are addicted to worship and not connected with heart to the world 200 persons were separated. These started advising to the others about not to do wickedness and to do good things of them. If they are, they killed all of these in one day since they got angry even because of these advises. Upon this incident a disagreement and sedition appeared between us. We left them; came to seaside, to beach. We prayed and begged to God to save us from their sinister. Upon this, a passage opened in front of us. We entered. After we resided under the ground 18 months, we went out from here to this place we exist." Additionally they said, that "Moses desired us to say his salute to you when we saw your face. Thanks to God, that we have been seen your face. Teach us Koran." [Hammami, Yâsîn]

[LOG 33a] The words smells alien. Seems the escaping people are from underground; but I think also they can be from space somewhere. Are these or from that lost clan of Jewry?

[LOG 34]

They will not believe in it, while there has already occurred the precedent of the former peoples. Even if We opened to them a gate from the heaven and they continued therein to ascend, They would still say, "Our eyes have only been dazzled. Rather, we are a people affected by magic." [Koran 15:13,14,15]

[LOG 34a] Very important record. There is a call for the people of 7th Century, and also the example was not given accidentally. Some people might be experienced this before. There is a hardly strong relation between the ancient nations and the people of our time, after 7th Century. This example might be given for that persons in [LOG 33]. Jewry was nested with miracles. Even many miracles. This was usual for them, and usually their problem was different than believing in God and his miracles.

[LOG 35]

As for those who defy God's revelations, and kill the prophets unjustly, and kill those who advocate justice among the people—promise them a painful retribution. They are those whose deeds will come to nothing, in this world and in the resurrection; and they will have no saviors. [Koran 3:21,22]

Muhammad says, "Torment of those people are more brutally, that they kill prophet or kill the person who forbids badness and advises goodness. Once children of Israel murdered 43 prophets in 1 hour at the beginning of a day. There 170 men came up between them, who forbids badness and advises goodness for that cruel people who murdered the prophets. At the end of the same day, also all of them had been murdered. These who God talks about them in these verses." [İbn Kesir]

[LOG 35a] As if to point those people Jewry experienced interstellar journey.

[LOG 35b] There are different people numbers in these texts; but this is not important. The important is the phenomenon itself.

Acknowledgment

I only translated some of them like the People of Mount Qaf Side, Gog and Magog and Interstellar Earthling since there is no English translation. I do not know where did I found the other ones. I was searching and copying many information before eliminating. As there is no jurisprudence about text itself, I did not give reference. If it is not legal, excuse me; because I do not care; but thanks for the translations. I just did not want to give the references without text.

Also I checked text references up carefully; but there still may mistakes. Since the phenomenon itself is important, I included some weak texts even if I do not know the actual references; so you can follow the text itself to search.

Also there are many information on stone. The Emerald Tablets and The Sumerian Tablets include many information. I do not know the emerald tablets since could not find the references to stay away from wrong information; but here exist many and trusted information about Sumerian Tablets: <http://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/>

There may some mistakes in the language.